

Impact of a primary care-based mobile health intervention to ‘sit less and move more’ on HbA1c, blood pressure, and other clinical outcomes in office employees with type 2 diabetes: A randomized controlled trial

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ABSTRACT

Background: Type 2 diabetes (T2D) is a prevalent and costly disease, with sedentary behaviour and physical inactivity as modifiable contributors. Mobile health (mHealth) applications provide complementary strategies for T2D management, but their impact on clinical outcomes remains unclear.

Objective: This study evaluated the efficacy of an mHealth programme promoting “sit less and move more” at work, prescribed in clinical practice, on clinical and cardiovascular risk factors in office employees with T2D.

Methods: A randomized controlled trial compared usual care (n = 25) with a 13-week mHealth intervention (n = 29) using the Walk@Work-App and web-based tools. Outcomes included HbA1c, glycemia, lipid profile, domain-specific sedentary behaviour (Workforce Sitting Questionnaire), objective physical activity and sedentary behaviour (ActivPal), blood pressure, and BMI at baseline, 6, and 12 months.

Results: Compared to the control group and at 12 months, the intervention group showed a significant reduction in HbA1c (p < 0.05), systolic and diastolic blood pressure (p < 0.05). Sitting time decreased during leisure activities while watching TV (p = 0.0052) and using electronic devices (p = 0.0397). The number of sedentary breaks and time spent in sedentary bouts <20 min/day increased (p < 0.05).

Conclusions: An mHealth programme effectively reduced sedentary behaviour, improved HbA1c and blood pressure, serving as a cost-effective lifestyle intervention for adults with T2D.

Trial registration: ClinicalTrials.gov NCT04092738. <https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/NCT04092738>

1. Background

Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2D) affected 10.5 % of the world population between 20 and 79 years of age in 2021, and it is forecasted to increase to 12.2 % in 2045 [1]. In 2021 it was responsible for 11 % of annual deaths, and it accounted for a significant burden in healthcare spending, including outpatient and hospital care, pharmaceutical

products and emergency care [2,3]. Cardiovascular disease is one of the main causes of morbidity and mortality in people with T2D [4]. It is estimated that more than 75 % of adults with diabetes over the age of 40 will die of a cardiovascular disease and are more likely than adults without diabetes to die in their first cardiovascular event [5]. Therefore, in adults with T2D it is essential to emphasize glycemic control and the management of cardiovascular risk factors associated with diabetes [4].

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Sedentary behaviour (SB) and physical inactivity –promoted by increasingly sedentary jobs [6]– have a high prevalence in adults with T2D [7,8] and are two of the main modifiable risk factors for the prevention, development and management of glucose intolerance (IGT or prediabetes) and T2D [9]. In adults with T2D, the prevalence of SB and physical inactivity is related to a higher rate of cardiovascular morbidity and mortality [9]. SB is defined as any waking behaviour while in a sitting, reclining or lying posture characterized by an energy expenditure ≤ 1.5 times the basal metabolic rate or metabolic equivalent of task (MET) [10]. The SB pattern is defined as the manner in which SB is accumulated throughout the day while awake, including the total sedentary time, the number of sedentary interruptions/breaks daily (a non-sedentary bout in between two sedentary bouts), the frequency and duration of the sedentary bouts (a period of uninterrupted sedentary time), and the time accumulated in each period [10].

Adults with T2D have shown to have a pattern of SB that is different from adults without diabetes [11], characterized by having fewer daily SB interruptions and spending less time sitting in short periods of less than 20 min [11]. Modifying these characteristic sedentary patterns of adults with T2D could tackle a modifiable risk factor for T2D [12] that is scarcely addressed from clinical practice, which mainly focuses on increasing moderate and vigorous activity [13].

Mobile health programmes (mHealth; i.e. medical healthcare interventions carried out through smart phones) [14] are an opportunity to address risk factors that are rarely treated in clinical practice, such as SB [12,13]. mHealth programmes improve accessibility to health services, improve access to information, provide patients with real-time information, and allow patients to monitor their own data [15]. However, the prescription of mHealth programmes from healthcare practice is scarce due to the lack of randomized controlled trials that determine their effectiveness on clinical outcomes [16,17]. In this regard, the short-, medium-, and long-term impact of mHealth programmes in modifying the SB pattern in the clinical population is unclear.

The Walk@Work Application (W@W-App) is an automated mobile phone and web-based intervention that focuses on decreasing and breaking up prolonged occupational sitting time in desk-based office employees. The W@W-App includes a self-monitoring tool that adds a commercially available sensor (MetaWearC; MbitentLab Inc) [18] covered with a waterproof round case and attached via a band to the thigh. The sensor gathers employees' postural and movement information during working hours. The W@W-App communicates with the MetaWearC external sensor via a low-energy Bluetooth System with postural and movement data being directly processed and displayed in real time by the app on the phone. W@W-App has been fully described elsewhere [19].

The objective of this randomized controlled trial is to evaluate the short-, medium- and long-term impact of prescribing the mHealth programme W@W-App from primary care consultations on glycemic control, HbA1c concentration and control of cardiovascular risk factors (HBP, DLP, obesity, sedentary behaviour and physical inactivity) in adults with T2D with sedentary or office jobs.

2. Methods

2.1. Study design

This study is a parallel, single-blind, randomized controlled trial (RCT) that enrolled 54 eligible adults with T2D with a 1:1 allocation. 29 and 25 patients were randomly assigned to the intervention (mHealth programme) and control (usual care) groups, respectively. The RCT protocol to evaluate the effectiveness of this healthcare-based mobile intervention on sedentary patterns, physical activity and clinical outcomes in office employees with T2D has been described elsewhere [19]. This RCT was registered at ClinicalTrials.gov (identification number: NCT04092738) and has been written in accordance with the new CONSORT-EHEALTH checklist (Multimedia Appendix 1

CONSORT-EHEALTH V1.6).

2.2. Participants and procedure

The recruitment of participants was carried out in three primary health care centres in Barcelona (Spain) between March and April 2019. A total of 75 adults at working age (between 18 and 65 years old) that had a diagnosis of T2D in accordance with international criteria were invited [20]. Participants were recruited randomly, initially by phone and, if they accepted, later through a face-to-face assessment in the consulting room. Participating patients were eligible if they had a smartphone, were office workers with a minimum of 55 % of their daily working hours performing sedentary tasks according to the Occupational Sitting and Physical Activity Questionnaire (OSPAQ) [21] and had a work contract of at least 18.5 h/week.

Exclusion criteria included having a diagnosis of musculoskeletal, cardiovascular, pulmonary, or orthopedic problems or any other physical condition that prevented them from being physically active, participating simultaneously in another study or programme targeting SB, physical activity, nutrition or weight control, being pregnant or having a history of psychiatric problems or substance abuse that could interfere with adherence to the study protocol.

In March 2019, three primary health care centres participated simultaneously, inviting a total of 75 patients. 54 agreed to participate and 21 were excluded, from which 13 failed to meet the inclusion criteria and 8 declined to participate (5 due to lack of time for self-care and 3 due to lack of interest/motivation). A detailed description of the study procedure has been published elsewhere [19].

2.3. Randomization and blinding

After obtaining patients' informed consent to participate in the trial, participants were randomized into the intervention or control group. Randomization was performed in a 1:1 ratio using a computerized random number generator. A data manager with no other involvement in the study conducted the randomization. The researcher responsible for implementing the intervention was the only person who was informed about group allocation. The research team, in charge of recording and monitoring the clinical data, was blinded to the randomization of the patient group. Patients were blinded to the existence of other patients receiving the intervention or being in a control group. The independent investigator who assessed the participants at the end of the intervention and at follow-ups was blinded to the participants' group allocation. In addition, the person who performed the data analysis was not involved in the data collection.

2.4. Measures

Participants' clinical outcomes and sociodemographic characteristics (age, gender and social class) were obtained from participants' clinical history and a baseline questionnaire completed during practice consultation respectively (see study protocol) [19].

The clinical variables of the study were the percentage (mean, standard deviation (SD)) of glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1c), glucose level (mg/dl; mean, SD), the level of total cholesterol (mg/dl; mean, SD), low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C) (mg/dl; mean, SD), high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-C) (mg/dl; mean, SD) and triglycerides (mg/dl; mean, SD). The variables were measured from fasting blood samples at baseline and at the 6- and 12-month follow-ups. Measurements were taken as part of the blood samples that were routinely taken in primary health care centres from adults with T2D.

Blood pressure and body mass index (BMI) were measured at baseline, 6- and 12-month follow-ups during practice consultations (see study protocol) [28]. Blood pressure was measured using a validated OMRON M3 sphygmomanometer following the recommendations of the European Society of Hypertension [22]. Three measurements were

taken in the consultations in sitting position with digital recordings, each at least 5 min apart, with the mean of the last two readings used for analyses. Participants' weight (kg) and height (m²) variables were measured with an approved Seca 770 scale and a height measuring rod Seca 222. The BMI (mean, SD) was calculated by dividing the body weight by the square of the height in metres (kg/m²). The BMI variable was classified into three groups: normal (18.5–24.9 kg/m²), overweight (≥ 25 kg/m² and < 30) and obesity (≥ 30 kg/m²), in accordance with current guidelines from the World Health Organization (WHO) [23].

Measurements for objective habitual occupational SB and physical activity were taken at the beginning and at a 3-month follow-up using the activPAL3™ device during practice consultations. Before randomization, all participants wore the activPAL3™ accelerometer for 7 consecutive days during waking hours, in line with the standard protocol for sedentary behaviour measurement. This baseline data collection occurred after informed consent and before any allocation to study groups. The activPAL3™ measured and quantified the sedentary behaviour patterns and physical activity of employees across weekdays. Data was processed using activPAL Professional Software™ (version 7.2.32), Microsoft Excel 2010 (Redmond, WA, USA), and MATLAB v8.4 (MathWorks®, Natick, MA, USA), following previously published protocols [24]. Resulting from the activPAL3™ software output, the following outcomes were determined: standing time (min/day), total sedentary breaks (number/day), number of sedentary breaks with four different lengths (< 20 min, 20–40 min, 40–60 min and > 60 min), time spent in sedentary bouts and time spent on four different lengths of sedentary bouts (< 20 min, 20–40 min, 40–60 min and > 60 min). Additionally, total time spent in light-intensity physical activity and moderate-to-vigorous physical activity was determined using previously validated count-to-activity thresholds [25].

Subjective measurements of domains for SB were taken at the beginning and at 6- and 12-month follow-ups during practice consultations (see study protocol) [19] using a seven-day total and domain-specific sitting time questionnaire (Workforce Sitting Questionnaire, WSQ) [26]. Participants completed the WSQ, which asked about sitting time (minutes/day; mean, SD) during workdays and non-workdays on the previous 7 days (1) while travelling to and from places; (2) while at work; (3) while watching TV; (4) while using a computer, tablet or smartphone at home; and (5) while doing other leisure activities. Subjective measurements for physical activity were taken at baseline during practice consultations using the Spanish version of a Brief Physical Activity Assessment Tool (SBPAAT), which identified participants who were insufficiently active versus those who followed the health recommendations for physical activity [27].

2.5. Sample size

An initial sample size of 220 participants was estimated, 110 in the intervention group and 110 in the control group, considering a 20 % loss to follow-up and 95 % statistical power. The study began in March 2019, and by the end of the same year, SARS-CoV-2 appeared in Wuhan (China), which spread worldwide and completely changed people's lives and habits, and, of course, ongoing clinical studies. As a result, losses were 45 % higher than initially estimated. Additionally, participants who, during the follow-up or at the beginning of the intervention, coincided with the onset or the course of the COVID-19 pandemic were excluded from the study.

With a final sample size of 54 participants and using the free software G*Power [28] for a two-sided mean comparison test, no significant differences between the two groups were found. With a significance level of 5 % and a mean effect size of 0.5 ($d = (\mu_1 - \mu_2) / \sigma$), the power of the test was determined to be 0.69. When the effect of the intervention was verified with the one-sided test, the power was 0.80. Multimedia Appendix 2 shows the power of the mean comparison test for independent samples, with both the two-sided and one-sided tests. Generally, a power value of 0.80 is acceptable and can be used as a reference point

[29].

2.6. The mHealth intervention: Walk@Work-App

The mHealth intervention W@W-App has been described elsewhere [19]. Briefly, participants registered, configured and installed the complete W@W-App in their own mobile phones during practice consultations for 13 weeks, the period during which participants wore a band with the attached external sensor on their thigh (see study protocol) [19]. The band was worn only during working hours, including the time taken to go to and back from work. During Week 0, the W@W-App provided self-monitoring features to get baseline measurements for occupational stepping, sitting and standing time and set up a programme baseline with individual targets for each employee. During Weeks 1–12, the app kept self-monitoring and displayed employees' occupational activity in real-time at the bottom of the screen. Daily and weekly motivational messages in the mobile screen reported the progress made on the achievement of individual targets. In the W@W-App website, graphs showed continuous feedback from week 0 to week 12 in relation to the goals that should have been achieved throughout the programme.

During weeks 1–12, participants had access to automated strategies to sit less and move more at work during an 8-week ramping phase (40 working days) and a 4-week maintenance phase. During the ramping phase, every two weeks employees were challenged to progressively increase their movement by replacing occupational sitting time with 10 min (Weeks 1–2), 20 min (Weeks 3–4), 30 mins (Weeks 5–6) or 37 min (Weeks 7–8) of moving or stepping above the average baseline (Week 0). During the maintenance phase (weeks 9–12), participants were challenged to keep reducing daily sitting time and increase movement or walking time by 40–60 min a day. Strategies have been described in detail elsewhere [19].

Throughout the programme, the W@W-App provided a range of effective behaviour change techniques to reduce and break up sitting time and increase physical activity at work [30].

The behaviour change techniques included in W@W-App were: (i) Feedback on behaviour and outcomes of behaviour (e.g. providing real-time feedback on the behaviours at the time when they occur); (ii) Self-monitoring of behaviour and outcomes of behaviour (e.g. providing graphics and messages with individual feedback on progress); (iii) Information about health consequences (e.g. providing articles on the health benefits of replacing sitting time with physical activity); (iv) Goal setting (i.e. setting goals every 2 weeks for reducing occupational sitting time and increasing moving); (v) Action Planning (e.g. providing groups of strategies that are progressively planned to increasing the length of the breaks in sitting time); (vi) Social support (i.e. providing a social network for sharing experiences and strategies using twitter or the blog); (vii) Instructions on how to perform the behaviour (e.g. providing detailed instructions of the tasks that can be done to reduce occupational sitting); and (H) Prompts (e.g. using coloured chairs).

2.7. Statistical analysis

A descriptive study of all the measured variables included the mean and standard deviation. The homogeneity between the CG and IG was verified at the starting time that is, no statistically significant differences were found between both groups in any of the variables measured at baseline.

For the quantitative variables, a bilateral mean comparison test was performed and for the qualitative variables, a chi-square test was performed to study the homogeneity between the variables and the group to which the patient belonged.

To study whether the variables improved with the intervention, the difference between the values of the variables to be studied at time t (3, 6 or 12 months) and the initial time ($t = 0$) were calculated.

The intervention had a positive effect on the measured variables if an increase or decrease in the value of the difference was observed,

depending on whether the patient’s results improved by increasing or decreasing the result of the variable. To detect a statistically significant increase or decrease in the IG with respect to the CG, a one-tailed t test of means was performed.

2.8. Ethical considerations

This study was approved by the Clinical Research Ethics Committee of the Primary Care Research Institute Jordi Gol with the registration code P18/102. All participants provided written informed consent prior to participation. All participant data were anonymized and they did not receive any compensation.

3. Results

3.1. Subject participation

A total of 70 participants were assessed for eligibility, of which 10 were excluded (8 did not meet the inclusion criteria and 2 declined to participate). 60 individuals were eligible and were randomly assigned. In the intervention group (n = 30), one participant (3 %) declined to participate, and 29 participants (96 %) completed the trial. In the control group (n = 30), 25 participants (83 %) completed the follow-up. Thus, a total of 54 participants completed the RCT and follow-up measures. The mhealth programme consisted of an 8-week ramping phase (40 working days) and a 4-week maintenance phase (20 working days).

Fig. 1. Flow Diagram. Schematic representation of the randomized controlled trial.

Regarding the intensity of use of the mhealth programme, 82 % of participants (n = 24) in the intervention group used the mhealth programme for at least 50 % of days during the ramping phase (Fig. 1).

3.2. Baseline characteristics of the study participants

Table 1 shows the baseline sociodemographic characteristics of the study participants as well as the clinical variables and cardiovascular risk factors. No statistically significant differences were observed between the intervention and control groups at the preliminary level in demographic characteristics and clinical variables. The mean age of the participants was 54.498 (SD 7.24) years, 42 (77.77 %) were men and more than half of the participants (57.4 %) had a university degree or diploma. 74 % and 72,9 % for the control and intervention group respectively did not report diet changes in the last 3 months. 66.7 % of the participants had normal SBP values (<140 mmHg), 76.8 % had normal DBP values (<90 mmHg), 11 % had normal BMI values (18.5 – 25 Kg/m²) and 28.4 % performed enough physical activity to meet the WHO recommendations.

The initial pattern of SB and physical activity of the adults with T2D participating in the study has been described elsewhere [11]. Table 2 describes this pattern according to the intervention and control groups.

Table 1
Baseline sociodemographic characteristics and clinical outcomes of the study participants (n = 99). Homogeneity of the groups at baseline.

Characteristics	Control (n = 25)	Intervention (n = 29)	p-value IC (95 %)
Demographics			
Age (years), mean (SD)	55.62 (6.93)	55.37 (7.56)	0.9032 [-4.21, 3.71]
Males, n (%)	21(84 %)	21(72.4 %)	
Female, n (%)	4 (16 %)	8 (27.6 %)	0.3093 [-0.11, 0.34]
I. Graduates or higher, company directors, n (%)	6 (24 %)	9 (31.03 %)	0.6927 [-1.17, 0.78]
II. Holding a university diploma, small entrepreneurs n (%)	8 (32 %)	8 (27,6 %)	
IIINM. Non-manual skilled, n (%)	1 (4.00 %)	2 (6.90 %)	
IIIM. Manual skilled, n (%)	3 (12 %)	5 (17.24 %)	
IV. Partially qualified, n (%)	3 (12 %)	2 (6.90 %)	
V. Not qualified, n (%)	3 (12 %)	3 (10.34 %)	
Doesn't know, n (%)	1 (4.00 %)	0 (0.00 %)	
BMI (k/m ²), mean (SD)	30.69 (5.56)	31.4 (6.2)	0.5549 [-2,50, 3,92]
Glycemia (mg/dl), mean (SD)	145.91 (68.63)	155.09 (53.88)	0.4607 [-25.02, 43.38]
Hemoglobin A1c (%), mean (SD)	7.28 (1.78)	7.42 (1.22)	0.6387 [-0.711, 0.991]
Total cholesterol (mg/dL), mean (SD)	179.67 (45.74)	190.18 (39.96)	0.2263 [-13.17, 34.19]
High-density lipoprotein cholesterol (mg/dL), mean (SD)	43.94 (13.99)	47.93 (14.92)	0.1726 [-3.91, 11.89]
Low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (mg/dL), mean (SD)	98.47 (40.69)	108.61 (37.07)	0.1978 [-11.28, 31.56]
Triglycerides (mg/dL), mean (SD)	163.33 (84.82)	168.87 (134.03)	0.8068 [-55.02, 66.10]
Systolic blood pressure (mmHg), mean (SD)	133.58 (15.05)	134.98 (15.51)	0.6497 [-6.96, 9.76]
Diastolic blood pressure (mmHg), mean (SD)	81.5 (11.23)	82.39 (10.1)	0.6625 [-4.99, 6.77]

SD, standard deviation.

Table 2
Baseline objective habitual sedentary behaviour and physical activity for study participants.

Characteristics	Control (n = 25)	Intervention (n = 29)	p-value
Total sedentary breaks (number/day), mean (SD)	49.97 (16.95)	44.81 (12.99)	0.1478
Sedentary breaks <20 min (number/day), mean (SD)	42.88 (16.72)	38.07 (12.84)	0.1722
Sedentary breaks of 20–40 min (number/day), mean (SD)	4.59 (1.61)	4.76 (1.72)	0.6550
Sedentary breaks of 40–60 min (number/day), mean (SD)	1.68 (0.65)	1.71 (0.78)	0.8603
Sedentary breaks >60 min (number/day), mean (SD)	1.65 (1.07)	1.87 (1.18)	0.3911
Total sedentary bout time (minutes/day), mean (SD)	568.04 (133.38)	564.36 (127.90)	0.9038
Time spent in sedentary bouts <20 min (minutes/day), mean (SD)	198.69 (67.29)	177.61 (60.93)	0.1618
Time spent in sedentary bouts 20–40 min (minutes/day), mean (SD)	127.92 (44.34)	132.62 (47.57)	0.6591
Time spent in sedentary bouts 40–60 min (minutes/day), mean (SD)	81.08 (31.61)	83.01 (37.70)	0.8100
Time spent in sedentary bouts >60 min (minutes/day), mean (SD)	160.35 (108.58)	171.12 (109.66)	0.6710
Standing time (minutes/day), mean (SD)	4.18 (1.57)	4.56 (1.73)	0.3281
Light-intensity physical activity (minutes/day)	79.8 (33)	70.2 (30.6)	0.1938
Moderate-to-vigorous physical activity (minutes/day)	38.4 (25.2)	42 (24)	0.5107

SD, standard deviation.

No statistically significant differences were observed between the two groups in SB and physical activity.

Table 3 shows time spent on various sedentary activities during the week and at the weekend of the adults with T2D that participated in the study. Most of the daily sedentary time was spent divided between work (326.275 min/day on average) and the use of computers, tablets or smartphones both on weekdays (350.95 min/day on average) and at

Table 3
Baseline subjective sedentary behaviour domains for study participants.

Characteristics	Control (n = 25)	Intervention (n = 29)	p-value
Sitting time while travelling to and from places on workdays (minutes/day), mean (SD)	105.6 (127.2)	90.6 (136.6)	0.5955
Sitting time while travelling to and from places on non-workdays (minutes/day), mean (SD)	95.7 (158.0)	67.1 (100.6)	0.3191
Sitting time while at work (minutes/day), mean (SD)	336.8 (133.3)	315.8 (162.2)	0.5069
Sitting time while watching TV on workdays (minutes/day), mean (SD)	140.1 (102.5)	128.2 (56.4)	0.5054
Sitting time while watching TV on non-workdays (minutes/day), mean (SD)	210.0 (130.5)	216.5 (102.9)	0.7966
Sitting time while using a computer, tablet or smartphone at home on workdays (minutes/day), mean (SD)	333.7 (151.0)	368.2 (110.0)	0.2291
Sitting time while using a computer, tablet or smartphone at home on non-workdays (minutes/day), mean (SD)	277.2 (167.7)	197.1 (128.6)	0.0147
Sitting time while doing other leisure activities on workdays (minutes/day), mean (SD)	93.2 (71.0)	82.4 (49.6)	0.4140
Sitting time while doing other leisure activities on non-workdays (minutes/day), mean (SD)	123.9 (101.3)	130.8 (76.2)	0.7237

SD, standard deviation.

weekends (237.16 min/day on average). No statistically significant baseline differences were observed between the groups.

3.3. Study outcomes

In comparison with the control group, participants in the intervention group had significant and clinically relevant reductions in glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c; $\leq -0.5\%$, $p < 0.01$) and in SBP and DBP ($p < 0.05$) at the 12-month follow-up (see Table 4). The maximum difference between the groups for HbA1c and SBP was observed at the 12-month follow-up (0.50% reduction in HbA1c concentration; 8.82 mm Hg reduction in SBP values).

No significant differences were found between groups regarding total cholesterol, HDL cholesterol, LDL cholesterol, triglycerides. The BMI results improved in the intervention group compared to the control group (see Table 4).

In comparison with the control group, the objective measures for SB and physical activity identified an increase in the number of daily sedentary breaks. Sixteen measurements were obtained (9 patients from the control group and 7 from the intervention group) during the 3-month follow-up, due to technical and logistical difficulties associated with primary care, which limited the available sample for this phase of the study. These results should be considered as approximations and confirmed in a new experimental phase. There was a greater number of SB breaks in the intervention group, with an average increase of 7.7 breaks/day, while in the control group the increase was 1.69 breaks/day. These differences were due to an increase in interruptions during periods of less than 20 min (see Table 5).

Compared to the control group and with regards to the sedentary time spent in different domains, significant differences were observed in the reduction of sitting time while at work of 45.63 min/day and 26.25 min/day at the 6- ($p < 0.01$) and 12-month follow-ups ($p < 0.05$), respectively. A significant reduction was also identified in sedentary time using a computer, tablet or smartphone at home on non-workdays ($p < 0.05$) and while doing other sedentary leisure activities on workdays of 10 min/day and 22 min/day at the 6- ($p < 0.05$) and 12-month follow-ups ($p < 0.05$), respectively (see Table 6).

4. Discussion

4.1. Principal findings

The objective of this randomized controlled trial was to evaluate the short-, medium-, and long-term impact of prescribing the mHealth W@W-App programme from primary care consultations on glycemic control and diabetes management variables (such as arterial hypertension, dyslipidemia, obesity, sedentary behaviour, and physical inactivity) in adults with T2D with sedentary or office jobs.

This study reported four main findings. First, the mHealth programme to “sit less and move more” at work in patients with T2D resulted in a clinically significant improvement in glycemic control, with a reduction at 12 months of 0.5 units in the percentage of HbA1c. The differences in HbA1c percentage were minimal at 6 months, but they became clinically and statistically significant at the 12-month follow-up. This pattern may reflect a delayed metabolic response (lag effect), in which behavioural changes initiated during the intervention take time to consolidate and manifest physiologically. Similar delayed effects have been described in other lifestyle and mHealth interventions [31,32], where improvements in HbA1c became evident several months after the end of the active intervention.

Second, the mHealth intervention produced an improvement in other main variables in the management of T2D (SBP and DBP). The differences in SBP and DBP units between the groups were also greater at 6 months but remained significant at 12 months. Third, the patients in the intervention group presented a greater number of SB breaks compared to the control group due to an increase in breaks in periods of

Table 4

Comparison of outcome measures between the two groups of the clinical variables and anthropometric parameters at baseline, 6 months and 12 months.

Parameters	Control (n = 25)	Intervention (n = 29)	P value IC (95 %)
Blood glucose (mg/dl) level (mg/dL), mean (SD)			
t = 0	145.91 (68.63)	155.09 (53.88)	0.4607 [−42.47, 24.11]
t = 6	128.67 (41.57)	150.47 (62.43)	0.2466 [−49.76, 6.16]
t = 12	177.67 (67.46)	148.8 (51.75)	0.0871 [−3.6, 61.34]
Mean difference (t = 0 and t = 6)	17.24 (50.18)	4.62 (64.94)	0.429 [−18.13, 43.37]
Mean difference (t = 0 and t = 12)	−31.76 (77.92)	6.29 (62.34)	0.062 [−76.10, 0]
Hemoglobin A1c (%), mean (SD)			
t = 0	7.28 (1.78)	7.42 (1.22)	0.6387 [−0.96, 0.69]
t = 6	7.29 (1.38)	7.30 (1.39)	0.99 [−0.75, 0.73]
t = 12	8.27 (1.56)	6.92 (1.2)	0.002 [−0.60, 2.10]
Difference (t = 0 and t = 6)	−0.01 (0.98)	0.12 (1.28)	0.677 [−0.73, 0.47]
Difference (t = 0 and t = 12)	−0.99 (2.64)	0.5 (1.27)	0.007 [−2.62, −0.36]
Total Cholesterol (mg/dl), mean (SD)			
t = 0	179.67 (45.74)	190.18 (39.96)	0.2263 [−33.60, 12.58]
t = 6	198.59 (45.84)	194.00 (36.57)	0.7490 [−17.77, 26.95]
t = 12	206.04 (45.08)	181.50 (48.05)	0.0568 [−0.32, 49.40]
Difference (t = 0 and t = 6)	−18.92 (39.92)	−3.82 (25.31)	0.111 [−33.26, 3.06]
Difference (t = 0 and t = 12)	−26.37 (44.79)	8.68 (20.98)	0.00110 [−54.20, −15.90]
HDL Cholesterol (mg/dl), mean (SD)			
t = 0	43.94 (13.99)	47.93 (14.92)	0.1726 [−11.71, 3.73]
t = 6	44.27 (20.5)	49.12 (10.53)	0.4187 [−13.75, 4.05]
t = 12	48.88 (11.17)	47.22 (11.47)	0.6431 [−4.39, 7.71]
Difference (t = 0 and t = 6)	−0.33(25.87)	−1.19 (6.30)	0.872 [−8.88, 11.92]
Difference (t = 0 and t = 12)	−4.94 (54.80)	0.71 (23.48)	0.635 [−28.77, 17.47]
LDL Cholesterol (mg/dl), mean (SD)			
t = 0	98.47 (40.69)	108.61 (37.07)	0.1978 [−31.03, 10.75]
t = 6	107.27 (55.33)	109.00 (41.71)	0.9219 [−28.20, 24.74]
t = 12	116.55 (31.67)	105.00 (30.66)	0.2505 [−5.14, 28.24]
Difference (t = 0 and t = 6)	−8.8 (35.63)	−0.39 (18.76)	0.3598 [−23.96, 7.14]
Difference (t = 0 and t = 12)	−18.08 (15.12)	3.61 (15.11)	0.4373 [6.38, 22.56]
Triglycerides (mg/dl), mean (SD)			
t = 0	163.33 (84.82)	168.87 (134.03)	0.8068 [−64.58, 53.50]
t = 6	139.06 (64.54)	168.82 (126.77)	0.3998 [−82.38, 22.86]

(continued on next page)

Table 4 (continued)

Parameters	Control (n = 25)	Intervention (n = 29)	P value IC (95 %)
t = 12	262.83 (106.9)	156.72 (62.45)	0.0247 [-58.44, 153.78]
Difference (t = 0 and t = 6)	24.27 (47.88)	0.05 (93.50)	0.3826 [-14.64, 63.08]
Difference (t = 0 and t = 12)	-99.5 (114.78)	12.15 (93.5)	0.0184 [-168.06, -55.24]
Systolic blood pressure (SBP) (mm Hg), mean (SD)			
t = 0	133.58 (15.05)	134.98 (15.51)	0.6497 [-9.57, 6.77]
t = 6	135.83 (12.58)	128.88 (16.11)	0.1666 [-0.71, 14.61]
t = 12	138.38 (14.23)	126.16 (11.37)	0.0026 [5.27, 19.17]
Difference (t = 0 and t = 6)	-2.25 (7.58)	6.1 (8.22)	0.0003 [-12.57, -4.13]
Difference (t = 0 and t = 12)	-4.8 (10.94)	8.82 (8.22)	0.000007 [-18.85, -8.39]
Diastolic blood pressure (DBP) (mm Hg), mean (SD)			
t = 0	81.5 (11.23)	82.39 (10.1)	0.6625 [-6.63, 4.85]
t = 6	80.28 (10.89)	75.59 (12.82)	0.2536 [-1.63, 11.01]
t = 12	82.35 (11.48)	73.89 (7.49)	0.0047 [3.20, 13.72]
Difference (t = 0 and t = 6)	1.22 (11.99)	6.8 (12.23)	0.097 [-12.05, 0.89]
Difference (t = 0 and t = 12)	-0.85 (12.22)	8.5 (11.86)	0.0065 [-15.80, -2.90]
Body Mass Index (BMI) (Kg/m²), mean (SD)			
t = 0	30.69 (5.56)	31.4 (6.2)	0.5549 [-3.85, 2.43]
t = 6	30.29 (4.97)	29.96 (4.94)	0.8482 [-2.32, 2.98]
t = 12	30.95 (6.5)	29.39 (6.52)	0.4364 [-1.92, 5.04]
Difference (t = 0 and t = 6)	0.4 (0.73)	1.44 (1.95)	0.0114 [-1.81, -0.27]
Difference (t = 0 and t = 12)	-0.26 (1.04)	2.01 (1.97)	0.000026 [-3.09, 1.45]

SD, standard deviation; T0: baseline, T6: at the 6-month follow-up; T12: at the 12-month follow-up, T6T0: difference between the baseline and the 6-month follow-up; T12T0: difference between the baseline and the 12-month follow-up. Positive values indicate a decrease from baseline (T0).

less than 20 min. Fourth, the adults with T2D in the intervention group showed a significant improvement in the reduction of sitting time while at work at both the 6- and 12-month follow-ups. The reduction of sitting time was observed in other domains of daily life on non-workdays and workdays, using a computer, tablet or smartphone at home on non-workdays or doing other leisure activities on workdays.

4.2. Comparison with the literature

This study supports the results of studies of interventions based on mobile technology to promote physical activity, reduce and break SB in adults with T2D that are effective [33]. There are few studies that measure the impact of mhealth interventions on promoting physical activity and reducing SB and HbA1c levels compared to usual care in patients with T2D in primary care.

In general, technological solutions for diabetes self-management use a feedback loop that uses patient-generated health data (PGHD) to adapt education and individualize feedback regarding HbA1C improvement [34,35]. Despite this, the majority of mobile applications for the management of T2D focus solely on the measurement and control of blood

Table 5

Comparison of outcome between the two groups at 3 months of the objective measures for sedentary behaviour and physical activity.

Parameters	Control (n = 10)	Intervention (n = 6)	P value
Total sedentary breaks (number/day), mean (SD)	-1.69 (6.33)	-7.70 (9.32)	0.0868
Sedentary breaks <20 min (number/day), mean (SD)	-1.57 (4.88)	-5.13 (9.03)	0.1867
Sedentary breaks of 20–40 min (number/day), mean (SD)	0.03 (1.69)	0.16 (2.16)	0.5541
Sedentary breaks of 40–60 min (number/day), mean (SD)	0.24 (0.92)	-0.42 (0.72)	0.0676
Sedentary breaks >60 min (number/day), mean (SD)	0.04 (0.75)	-0.34 (0.78)	0.1748
Total bout time, mean (SD)	7.84 (60.75)	-65.78 (106.24)	0.0681
Time spent in sedentary bouts <20 min (minutes/day), mean (SD)	-1.16 (25.43)	-33.45 (34.72)	0.0328
Time spent in sedentary bouts 20–40 min (minutes/day), mean (SD)	-0.18 (50.79)	7.47 (57.26)	0.6073
Time spent in sedentary bouts 40–60 min (minutes/day), mean (SD)	13.63 (44.37)	-20.08 (35.81)	0.0583
Time spent in sedentary bouts >60 min (minutes/day), mean (SD)	-4.45 (85.44)	-19.71 (57.67)	0.3387
Standing time (minutes/day), mean (SD)	-0.23 (0.45)	-1.14 (4.46)	0.3046
Light-intensity physical activity (minutes/day)	-0.07 (0.10)	-0.20 (0.54)	0.2799
Moderate-to-vigorous physical activity (minutes/day)	-0.12 (0.28)	-0.13 (0.45)	0.4692

SD, standard deviation.

glucose or in combination with diet, blood pressure control and weight or physical activity in a way that is not very detailed [35,36]. Few include changing the SB pattern as the main intervention strategy in the self-management of the disease. Despite the few studies of mobile applications where the main focus of the intervention is the pattern of physical activity and SB, mobile applications that include the promotion of physical activity, with automatic data transfer that promote motivation and increase physical activity have been shown to play an important role in T2D self-management [37].

The effect of technology-based interventions in patients with T2D on long-term clinical parameters is described in other studies, where the effects were not maintained at 12 months [36,38]. One factor that could explain the sustainability of the effect of the intervention at 12 months could be the 3-month duration of the intervention. Previous studies [39, 40] have reported a greater effect of longer interventions compared to shorter ones [41]. In addition, the patients synchronized the mobile application with a wearable device, which seems to be more effective [29,39] than interventions without such a device.

Several recent studies of mHealth programmes for T2D have highlighted the importance of help and clinical support from professionals to increase motivation, intervention adherence and potential clinical benefits [42,43]. A systematic review of the effectiveness of interventions that use applications to improve diet, physical activity and SB found evidence that interventions that combine personal advice were more successful than a mobile application alone [44].

Another aspect related to the potential benefit of the mhealth programme is that the scope of the intervention was focused on working hours, where a significant part of sedentary time accumulates, potentially having greater beneficial effects in the control of T2D and CVR factors. Interventions in the workplace can be an effective health promotion strategy, which has also been endorsed by the World Health Organization. In adults with T2D, the interruption of sedentary time with short, regular and frequent episodes of light-intensity physical activity such as walking or simple resistance activities attenuates the

Table 6

Comparison of outcome measures between the two groups of subjective sedentary behaviour domains at the start, and after 6 and 12 months.

Characteristics	Control (n = 25)	Intervention (n = 29)	P value
Sitting time while travelling to and from places on workdays (minutes/day), mean (SD)			
t = 0	105.60 (127.23)	90.61 (136.59)	0.5955
t = 6	110.16 (112.30)	94.38 (155.10)	0.3214
t = 12	111.33 (112.33)	79.17 (106.27)	0.1432
Difference (t = 0 and t = 6)	10.45 (73.81)	-6.19 (21.17)	0.1107
Difference (t = 0 and t = 12)	15.33 (67.77)	-8.25 (31.21)	0.0488 *
Sitting time while travelling to and from places on non-workdays (minutes/day), mean (SD)			
t = 0	95.71 (158.02)	67.07 (100.62)	0.3191
t = 6	84.53 (120.20)	66.56 (120.06)	0.2759
t = 12	94.17 (123.33)	71.46 (99.41)	0.2286
Difference (t = 0 and t = 6)	2.73 (43.48)	-6.09 (112.91)	0.3409
Difference (t = 0 and t = 12)	13.00 (49.16)	19.58 (102.38)	0.3871
Sitting time while at work (minutes/day), mean (SD)			
t = 0	336.79 (133.27)	315.76 (162.21)	0.5069
t = 6	356.67 (133.92)	272.81 (140.58)	0.0083 *
t = 12	347.00 (133.39)	274.58 (127.31)	0.0237 *
Difference (t = 0 and t = 6)	-1.52 (34.38)	-45.63 (49.90)	0.0001 *
Difference (t = 0 and t = 12)	-11.00 (95.68)	-26.25 (51.90)	0.2296
Sitting time while watching TV on workdays (minutes/day), mean (SD)			
t = 0	140.12 (102.48)	128.15 (56.37)	0.5054
t = 6	114.06 (56.73)	113.59 (55.19)	0.4867
t = 12	123.17 (70.47)	94.38 (33.53)	0.0273 *
Difference (t = 0 and t = 6)	-18.64 (77.67)	-17.19 (51.71)	0.4648
Difference (t = 0 and t = 12)	-10.00 (79.21)	-31.25 (51.38)	0.1199
Sitting time while watching TV on non-workdays (minutes/day), mean (SD)			
t = 0	210.00 (130.51)	216.52 (102.94)	0.7966
t = 6	179.06 (94.71)	182.81 (97.69)	0.4383
t = 12	174.00 (95.65)	178.75 (95.48)	0.4284
Difference (t = 0 and t = 6)	-7.27 (73.50)	-17.81 (54.87)	0.2570
Difference (t = 0 and t = 12)	0.00 (36.10)	-11.25 (66.68)	0.2311
Sitting time while using a computer, tablet or smartphone at home on workdays (minutes/day), mean (SD)			
t = 0	333.71 (151.04)	368.15 (110.03)	0.2291
t = 6	338.31 (107.34)	309.38 (114.41)	0.1504
t = 12	343.67 (131.27)	310.00 (114.89)	0.1601
Difference (t = 0 and t = 6)	-28.48 (120.00)	-60.94 (65.43)	0.0902
Difference (t = 0 and t = 12)	-3.53 (134.09)	-41.88 (70.07)	0.0915
Sitting time while using a computer, tablet or smartphone at home on non-workdays (minutes/day), mean (SD)			

Table 6 (continued)

Characteristics	Control (n = 25)	Intervention (n = 29)	P value
t = 0	277.19 (167.66)	197.13 (128.59)	0.0147*
t = 6	264.69 (145.29)	170.41 (108.32)	0.0023*
t = 12	276.00 (142.12)	166.25 (110.49)	0.0012*
Difference (t = 0 and t = 6)	-11.52 (72.38)	-31.41 (45.84)	0.0949
Difference (t = 0 and t = 12)	9.00 (40.29)	-27.83 (64.27)	0.0097*
Sitting time while doing other leisure activities on workdays (minutes/day), mean (SD)			
t = 0	93.21 (71.02)	82.39 (49.58)	0.4140
t = 6	102.19 (74.99)	69.06 (50.12)	0.0213*
t = 12	100.00 (76.92)	63.75 (39.87)	0.0153*
Difference (t = 0 and t = 6)	11.82 (36.70)	-10.00 (50.99)	0.0266*
Difference (t = 0 and t = 12)	6.00 (42.72)	-22.08 (45.59)	0.0126*
Sitting time while doing other leisure activities on non-workdays (minutes/day), mean (SD)			
t = 0	123.93 (101.31)	130.76 (76.20)	0.7237
t = 6	126.56 (89.43)	100.31 (67.13)	0.0947
t = 12	125.00 (74.78)	101.25 (58.56)	0.0982
Difference (t = 0 and t = 6)	-1.36 (37.94)	-18.75 (50.97)	0.0626
Difference (t = 0 and t = 12)	-4.50 (58.31)	-18.75 (49.90)	0.1690

SD, standard deviation; * There are statistically significant differences; T0: baseline T6: at the 6-month follow-up; T12: at the 12-month follow-up, T6T0: difference between the baseline and the 6-month follow-up; T12T0: difference between the baseline and the 12-month follow-up.

level of postprandial glucose, insulin, C-peptide and triglycerides [45], and reduces waist circumference, body mass index (BMI) [46] and blood pressure [47]. In our results there was a greater number of SB breaks in the intervention group, increasing 7.7 interruptions/day, mainly due to the increase in interruptions in periods of time less than 20 min, modifying the characteristic pattern in adults with T2D compared to adults without T2D [11], which can justify the results in the clinical improvements.

4.3. Strengths and limitations

This study has several strengths. First, we found that the effectiveness of mHealth programme interventions on sedentary time, physical activity, and clinical outcomes in adults with chronic diseases has been evaluated in very few studies. Our study is one of the few that evaluates the impact of the intervention to "sit less and move more" at work in adults with T2D from clinical practice in primary care, compared to usual care.

Second, one of the main strengths was that the control group was not active and received usual care. This fact helps explain that part of the clinical improvement detected is due to the intervention. However, it is possible that patients in the intervention group had more visits with health professionals, as a result of the intervention itself, compared to the control group. It was not possible to blind the professionals to the mHealth programme intervention, as the patients consulted with the health professionals on aspects related to the programme. Even so, the participating professionals received prior training and support to limit their inquiries to technical issues regarding the mobile app, rather than health advice.

Third, the mHealth programme included behaviour change techniques, goals, planning, feedback, monitoring, social support, and rewards. Portable technology synchronized with the mobile application in real-time. Through the use of tracking devices and continuous feedback, participants became aware of their physical activity and behavioural patterns, allowing them to visualize and measure their achievements, thus increasing motivation to continue making changes to reach their goals.

Finally, other factors that might have influenced the results were taken into account, such as changes in diet and medication during the intervention and follow-up period. No differences in medication (insulinization and number of oral antibiotics) or changes in diet were observed between the groups during the intervention and follow-up period. Regarding changes in diet, there were no statistically significant differences between the two groups at the 3-, 6-, and 12-month follow-ups (p-value < 0.1342, p-value = 0.5595, and p-value = 0.1596, respectively). Future research should study the impact of these programmes on other modifiable risk factors such as diet type.

The main limitation was the sample size, as patient recruitment had to be completely suspended due to the COVID-19 pandemic, owing to legal restrictions, logistical issues, and operational problems related to the pandemic. This led to a reduction in the total sample of patients. Data from patients who were recruited later had to be excluded, as some of the follow-up periods coincided with the COVID-19 pandemic. The statistical power is lower than initially desirable, so we need to be cautious in the interpretation of the results. Despite this, the data generated are sufficient to indicate that the evaluated mHealth programme had an impact on the clinical variables and cardiovascular risk factors.

5. Conclusions and implications

Mobile app interventions to “sit less and move more” at work may be effective in decreasing and breaking sedentary time, improve glycemic control and the main cardiovascular risk factors in patients with T2D that are monitored in primary health care consultations. This is one of the first studies that evaluates the impact of the use of applications to “sit less and move more” in patients with diabetes on glucose control measured by hemoglobin A1c (HbA1c) levels and clinical parameters. Future research should increase the sample size for RCTs measuring ActivPal-based SB and PA levels.

The mHealth programmes to sit less and move more could be used as an additional strategy to address SB that is not often dealt with in clinical practice in primary health care in patients with T2D [11]. T2D generates enormous social and health costs and reducing HbA1C levels could lead to economic savings. Financing mHealth programmes that can complement the usual care of adults with T2D could be a measure to alleviate the high pressure on healthcare and the limited resources of the healthcare system.

Future research is needed on the optimal number and combination of

application characteristics and behaviour change techniques to maximize intervention effectiveness [45], and also to know the factors that increase the use of the application, the continuous participation of the healthcare professionals and the reminders [48] and maintain the effects on the clinical results of the intervention in the medium-long term. Given that lifestyle changes take time and require reinforcement, a longer intervention period with continuous support (i.e. health advice) may be needed for sustained behavioural changes that lead to better control of diabetes.

Author contributions

FA, MAC, JBR, CPE, CZY, CMC and APR were responsible for the conception and design of the study. MAC was responsible for the sample size calculation and conceived the statistical methods. FA, APR, JBR, CZY, and CPR participated in the development of the study. All authors have performed a critical revision of this manuscript and the final version.

Protocol

Alòs F, Colomer MÀ, Martin-Cantera C, et al. Effectiveness of a healthcare-based mobile intervention on sedentary patterns, physical activity, mental well-being and clinical and productivity outcomes in office employees with type 2 diabetes: study protocol for a randomized controlled trial. *BMC Public Health*. 2022;22(1):1269. Published 2022 Jun 29. doi:10.1186/s12889-022-13676-x.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix 1

CONSORT 2010 checklist of information to include when reporting a randomized trial*

Section/Topic	Item No	Checklist item	Reported on page No
Title and abstract	1a	Identification as a randomized trial in the title	Page 1, lines 1–3
	1b	Structured summary of trial design, methods, results, and conclusions (for specific guidance see CONSORT for abstracts)	Page 1, lines 4–28
Introduction Background and objectives	2a	Scientific background and explanation of rationale	Page 2, lines 36–64 Page 3, lines 65–78 Page 3, lines 79–83
	2b	Specific objectives or hypotheses	
Methods Trial design	3a	Description of trial design (such as parallel, factorial) including allocation ratio	Page 3, lines 87–92
	3b	Important changes to methods after trial commencement (such as eligibility criteria), with reasons	N/A
Participants	4a	Eligibility criteria for participants	Page 3, lines 96–97 Page 4, lines 98–103 Page 4, lines 109–113
	4b	Settings and locations where the data were collected	Page 6, lines 195–201 Page 7, lines 202–230
Interventions	5	The interventions for each group with sufficient details to allow replication, including how and when they were actually administered	Page 4, lines 127–132 Page 4, lines 133–166 Page 5, lines 168–177
Outcomes	6a	Completely defined pre-specified primary and secondary outcome measures, including how and when they were assessed	N/A
	6b	Any changes to trial outcomes after the trial commenced, with reasons	Page 6, lines 180–193
Sample size	7a	How sample size was determined	N/A
	7b	When applicable, explanation of any interim analyses and stopping guidelines	N/A
Randomization: Sequence generation	8a	Method used to generate the random allocation sequence	Page 4, lines 114–124
	8b	Type of randomization; details of any restriction (such as blocking and block size)	Page 4, lines 115–117
Allocation concealment mechanism	9	Mechanism used to implement the random allocation sequence (such as sequentially numbered containers), describing any steps taken to conceal the sequence until interventions were assigned	Page 4, lines 113–117
Implementation	10	Who generated the random allocation sequence, who enrolled participants, and who assigned participants to interventions	Page 4, lines 117–118
Blinding	11a	If done, who was blinded after assignment to interventions (for example, participants, care providers, those assessing outcomes) and how	Page 4, lines 118–120
	11b	If relevant, description of the similarity of interventions	N/A
Statistical methods	12a	Statistical methods used to compare groups for primary and secondary outcomes	Page 7, lines 232–236 Pages 8, lines 237–241
	12b	Methods for additional analyses, such as subgroup analyses and adjusted analyses	N/A
Results			
Participant flow (a diagram is strongly recommended)	13a	For each group, the numbers of participants who were randomly assigned, received intended treatment, and were analysed for the primary outcome	Fig. 1
	13b	For each group, losses and exclusions after randomization, together with reasons	Fig. 1
Recruitment	14a	Dates defining the periods of recruitment and follow-up	Page 4, lines 96–97
	14b	Why the trial ended or was stopped	N/A
Baseline data	15	A table showing baseline demographic and clinical characteristics for each group	Table 1, Table 2, Table 3
Numbers analysed	16	For each group, number of participants (denominator) included in each analysis and whether the analysis was by original assigned groups	Fig. 1
Outcomes and estimation	17a	For each primary and secondary outcome, results for each group, and the estimated effect size and its precision (such as 95 % confidence interval)	Page 12, lines 302, Pages 13–16
	17b	For binary outcomes, presentation of both absolute and relative effect sizes is recommended	N/A
Ancillary analyses	18	Results of any other analyses performed, including subgroup analyses and adjusted analyses, distinguishing pre-specified from exploratory	N/A
Harms	19	All important harms or unintended effects in each group (for specific guidance see CONSORT for harms)	N/A
Discussion Limitations	20	Trial limitations, addressing sources of potential bias, imprecision, and, if relevant, multiplicity of analyses	Page 19, lines 445–452
	21	Generalisability (external validity, applicability) of the trial findings	Page 20, lines 456–160 Page 20, line 462–467
Generalisability			
Interpretation	22	Interpretation consistent with results, balancing benefits and harms, and considering other relevant evidence	Page 17, lines 356–389 Page 18, lines 390–415
Other information			
Registration	23	Registration number and name of trial registry	Page 3, lines 92–93
Protocol	24	Where the full trial protocol can be accessed, if available	Page 3, lines 89–92
Funding	25	Sources of funding and other support (such as supply of drugs), role of funders	Page 20, lines 480–495 Page 21, lines 496–497

*We strongly recommend reading this statement in conjunction with the CONSORT 2010 Explanation and Elaboration for important clarifications on all the items. If relevant, we also recommend reading CONSORT extensions for cluster randomized trials, non-inferiority and equivalence trials, non-pharmacological treatments, herbal interventions, and pragmatic trials. Additional extensions are forthcoming: for those and for up to date references relevant to this checklist, see www.consort-statement.org.

Appendix 2

Power of the mean comparison test for independent samples, a) bilateral test, b) unilateral test.

Data availability

The data sets generated during and/or analyzed during this study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

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